

The Concept Of The Bridge-Bank And Its Legal Nature And The Extent Of Its Impact On The Financial Transactions Of Individuals

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 17, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 18, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Banking Activity, Global Economy, The Principles Of Governance, The National Economy</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5576604</p>	<p><i>Banking activity is one of the most prominent areas of the economic sector and therefore it affects and is negatively and positively affected by the developments of the global economy significantly, and this is evident at the present time, as it has become reliance on technology in programming and implementing banking business, by focusing on the principles of governance, transparency, protection and assistance to the consumer and this is the effect positive. As for the negative effect it is represented by the economic obstacles and setbacks that were reflected on the banking sector in many countries and all this is reflected in the national economy of each country. Finally, these crises led to the phenomenon of banking insolvency and this was reflected in the national banking sector and which leads to the withdrawal of investors and the transfer of cash flows to other economic destinations.</i></p> <p><i>As for banking default, the jurisprudence agreed on the general idea of it, which is that bank default means the debtor's inability to fulfil his obligation, and this concept is consistent with the legal view of the banking institution. This undoubtedly affects the confidence of dealers in the national economy and the banking institution, and this is what made us look for any secondary means that would focus public confidence in the banking sector.</i></p>

Introduction

The banking sector in Iraq has suffered from major problems in all its joints since 2003 until now, and this is due to many reasons known to all. Through these problems and the resulting deterioration, many banks, especially the private ones, are exposed to insolvency or bankruptcy and their inability to fulfil their financial obligations with their customers and with the Central Bank of Iraq. In these cases, the central bank, as the supreme financial authority in the country, takes a package of legal measures to try to save the insolvent bank from bankruptcy and to protect the rights of all the parties concerned, including depositors, investors, institutions, and others. Among these procedures permitted by the Iraqi Banking Law No. 94 of 2004, and according to Article 61 of it, is the establishment of a (bridge-bank). It is a temporary bank owned and managed by the Central Bank of Iraq. Which is established, licensed, recapitalized and operated, with the aim of addressing, rehabilitating and evaluating the business of an insolvent bank by transferring the assets and liabilities of that insolvent bank to the bridge bank, which in turn manages the operations of the insolvent bank for a period of up to two years and may be extended for a third year and for the purpose of evaluating the work of this bank and overcome his problems and to allow the opportunity to find a buyer during that period, This transfer does not require the approval of the bank subject to qualification or any of its management bodies.

Accordingly, we will explain the concept of the bridge bank by dividing this topic into several demands. In the first requirement, we show the definition of the bridge bank, while we dedicate the second requirement to the legal nature of the bridge bank.

The first requirement

The definition of the bridge-bank

The bridge bank is of a temporary nature, as the central bank undertakes its establishment and management in order to treat, rehabilitate and evaluate the work of another troubled bank. In view of the newness of this type of banks in the Iraqi arena, several names have appeared for this type of banks. We believe that it is not intended on the part of the legislator and did not reflect a specific judgment, nor did it stem from the opinions of jurists and writers, but rather as a result of the multiple terms that the Iraqi Banking Law came with due to the confusion in its formulation caused by the circumstances of its issuance by the so-called (Coalition Provisional Authority) and then translated into the Arabic language. Accordingly, we will divide this requirement into two sections. In the first section, we explain the definition of the bridge bank, and the second section for its objectives, while we dedicate the third section to the characteristics of the bridge bank.

First section

Definition of bridge bank

It is a temporary bank owned and managed by the Central Bank of Iraq, which is established, licensed, recapitalized and operated, with the aim of addressing, rehabilitating and evaluating the business of an insolvent bank by transferring the assets and liabilities of that insolvent bank to the bridge bank, which in turn manages the operations of the insolvent bank for a period of up to two years and may be extended for a third year to allow the insolvent bank to find a buyer during that period and after its evaluation. Such transfer does not require the approval of the bank subject to qualification or any of its management bodies, and the transfer of liabilities is published by means of a notice published in the Official Gazette and in two or more newspapers of general circulation determined by the Central Bank of Iraq.

The bridge bank also means moving from the stage of collapse to the stage of reorganization and restructuring for one of the banks, but not for the old bank, but for the good assets in whole or in part, and they are transferred to the bridge bank. The idea of the bridge bank has existed for a long time and many experiences have taken place in the world, most notably in the United States of America, as there are approximately (200) banks that have been converted into bridge banks and rehabilitated, and the idea has been applied in banks in some Arab countries, including Lebanon and Egypt.

The Iraqi Banking Law No. 94 of 2004 referred to the bridge bank on more than one occasion and under more than one title, including the interim bank, the bridge bank, and the intermediary bank. Where Article (1) of this Law indicates and under the heading (Defining Terms), the term “interim bank” means the bank formed under Paragraph (6) of Article 61.

While Article 61 Paragraph (6) referred to “bridge banks” in the text “...the Central Bank of Iraq may, according to its choice, organize a license for a bridge bank owned and controlled by the Central Bank of Iraq”.

As the legislator explained in Chapter Twelve (Rehabilitation of Banks) in Article 67/3 the rehabilitation procedures (... The Central Bank of Iraq may order the trustee to transfer part or all of the assets and liabilities to an intermediary bank that the state establishes and capitalizes...).

Whereas Article (67/a) of the same law stipulates that 1- The Central Bank of Iraq shall, according to its choice, establish and license a temporary bank based on Article (61/6), which is owned and managed by the Central Bank of Iraq.

And since the Iraqi legislator has intended in the above-mentioned texts the synonym of these terms, as they indicate one meaning, which is the establishment of a temporary bank owned and managed by the Central Bank of Iraq, which is established, licensed, recapitalized and operated. With the aim of treating, rehabilitating and evaluating the business of a troubled bank, by transferring the assets and liabilities of that troubled bank to the new (bridge) bank. Therefore, these names must be unified in one of them, and we believe that naming the interim bank is the most appropriate for the following reasons:

1-The name (the bridge bank) is far from the language of the law and unfamiliar, as it was mentioned in the law only once, and that is in Article (61/6).

2-The designation (intermediary bank) may not indicate the true meaning intended by the legislator, as the idea of the bridge bank does not focus on mediation between two banks as is clear from the definition, and the term “intermediary bank” may lead to confusion with other terms mentioned in the Trade Law, for example. As in the case of the mediation of a bank when opening a documentary credit, as well as in the case of a bank transfer between inside and outside, which requires the presence of an (intermediary bank) in the case of a compound bank transfer. Also, this name was mentioned only once in Article (67/3).

3- While the designation (interim bank) indicates the intended meaning, as it refers to the existence of a bank that performs a specific role and for a specific period of time after which it ends, and the Iraqi legislator used this term more than once on the occasion of establishing the interim bank, providing it with capital, and appointing members of the board of directors. Administration in it, determine its powers, and so on.

4-And most importantly, which indicates that the legislator’s intention has gone to the interim bank, or it is the most appropriate term, and that is what is stated in Article (1) of the law and under the title (Defining Terminology). The term (interim bank) means the bank that is constituted pursuant to paragraph (6) of Article (61).

Second section

Objectives of the bridge bank

The process of establishing and operating the bridge bank aims to employ the bank (and through the implementation of the rescue program and rehabilitation of the bank subject to rehabilitation and making it run its business on an ongoing basis). To avoid systemic financial risks to the national economy and the credit market and calm creditors and depositors in an attempt to avoid the negative effects resulting from bank failure and mismanagement and to enhance confidence and reassurance and ensure the preservation of the reputation and integrity of the banking system.

The main mission of the bridge bank is to:

1-Smooth transition from bank insolvency to continuous operations by rehabilitating the insolvent bank and continuously re-managing its business in the banking market.

2-Receiving and managing deposits Respecting the obligations of the troubled bank and ensuring that the service of depositors is not interrupted.

3-Manage the service of outstanding loan commitments and liquidate assets portfolio holdings in an orderly manner.

4-Managing all other assets and liabilities of the insolvent bank in accordance with the instructions of the banking supervisory authorities.

The main objective of the establishment of the bridge bank is to be a temporary and interim measure, hence the description of (the bridge), whose tasks are to implement a rescue program for the bank subject to rehabilitation, as the bridge bank provides the time necessary for the troubled bank to find a buyer during the rehabilitation period, which does not exceed two years and may be extended for a year third, with the approval of the Central Bank of Iraq, In the event that the bank subject to qualification is unable to find a buyer within the above period ceiling, then the bridge bank shall manage the liquidation operations of that bank.

The Central Bank has established the first bridge bank in Iraq, which is (Hammurabi Investment Bank), in order to solve the problems faced by (Dar Al Salam Investment Bank), whose previous administration failed to properly conduct its business and brought it to the brink of bankruptcy. The management of the Central Bank of Iraq converted it into a bridge bank and completely changed its management. This decision came from the Central Bank as the authority concerned with achieving stability for the banking sector by following up and monitoring banks and trying to find appropriate solutions to the cases and problems they are exposed to and to save the troubled bank and return life to its financial activities and transition From the guardianship stage to the bridge bank stage, that is, instead of forced liquidation, work to achieve a noble goal, which is to preserve the rights of depositors in banks and to avoid any harm to shareholders or other parties, and for the purpose of addressing the phenomenon of banking failure without resorting to final financial liquidation. The measure taken by the Central Bank is a sound financial measure and allowed by the Iraqi Banking Law, even if this first experience in the world of Iraqi banks succeeded, and if the new management of the bank was able to apply standards of compliance, control, internal control and international accounting standards, establish a network of correspondents with the rules of international banks and adopt risk management In all its forms, especially in the field of managing the separation of management from property rights to avoid conflicting banking interests and to achieve risk-sharing between management and owners of property rights. More importantly, if it brings the bank to safety and restores confidence to customers and depositors, this experience will be an incentive for the Central Bank to generalize it to all troubled banks to promote the Iraqi banking sector, which is going through its worst condition reconstruction and investment in all sectors and this will not be achieved properly except in the presence of a sober and stable banking sector that is free of corruption.

There are successful global experiences regarding the idea of the bridge (interim) bank. In 2011, the Central Bank of Nigeria issued a decision to cancel the licenses of three banks that were beset with financial problems that they were unable to overcome and address, and three bridge banks were established and the assets and liabilities of those banks were transferred to them. Whereas, the Central Bank of Nigeria and the Deposit Insurance Corporation are authorized to manage and operate these bridge banks and to manage all assets and liabilities devolved to it from troubled banks, Bridge banks are also allowed to seek liquidation of failed banks either by finding buyers for the bank as a going concern, or by liquidating their portfolio of assets within two years which can be extended an additional year, If the bridge bank fails to scale down its operations within the stipulated time, the bridge bank shall notify the Governor of the Central Bank of Nigeria of its intention to dissolve the bridge bank, in which case the Deposit Insurance Corporation shall be designated as the receiver of the assets of the bridge bank. In the United States of America, under the Banking Regulation Act of the United States, the Bridge Bank is a temporary bank regulated by federal regulators to manage the deposits and obligations of a failing bank and under the Competitive Equity Banking Act of 1987, the Federal Deposit Insurance Corporation is authorized to establish and operate a bridge bank that must meet the obligations the failing bank of its customers and the failure to interrupt or terminate adequately secured loans, It also allows the bridge bank to seek to liquidate the failing bank either by searching for buyers for the bank as a going concern or by liquidating its portfolio of assets within two years which can be extended for another additional year, and if the bridge bank fails to reduce its operations within the specified period, the bridge bank must notify the controller The currency to dissolve the bridge bank and appoint the Federal Deposit Corporation as the recipient of the assets of the bridge bank.

Third section

Characteristics of the bridge bank

From the foregoing, it is clear that the bridge bank has the following characteristics:

1-Temporary Bank: The bridge bank, as we mentioned, is a temporary bank. As the Central Bank establishes, licenses, recitals and operates it, with the aim of treating and rehabilitating it and evaluating the work of another

(troubled) bank. This is by transferring the assets and liabilities of that bank to the bridge bank that manages the operations of the troubled bank for a period of up to two years unless the central bank extends the legal quality for three additional quarters during one year, to allow the troubled bank to find a buyer during that period, and this transfer does not require obtaining the approval of the bank subject to qualification or any of its management bodies.

2-Affiliated Bank: It is affiliated with the Central Bank of Iraq, which is responsible for appointing members of the board of directors for the bridge (interim) bank, provided that they are suitable persons, according to the expression of the Iraqi legislator. The Council also implements the terms of the bank's founding contract approved by the Central Bank, in addition to adopting all laws and instructions issued by this bank. The latter shall also appoint or dismiss any administrative or banking employee.

3-It is considered one of the public companies: the bridge bank is subject to the provisions of the Public Companies Law No. (22) of (1997) in terms of its establishment, management, capital, how to distribute its profits and losses, and liquidation, unless there is a special provision regarding it in the Iraqi Banking Law.

4- The bridge (interim) bank is not established except in the case of a troubled bank for which a guardian or a judicial guard has been appointed. This is what is understood from the text of Article (67/A) of the same law, which states that 1 The Central Bank of Iraq shall, according to its choice, establish and license a temporary bank based on Article (61/6), which is owned and managed by the Central Bank of Iraq. To receive any assets or liabilities from one or more banks for which a trustee has been appointed pursuant to Part (11) or a receiver under Part 14.

The second requirement

The legal nature of the bridge-bank

The legal texts related to the bridge bank contained in the Banking Law No. (94) for the year (2004), raise some questions about the legal nature of this bank. As these texts refer to the term articles of incorporation... as it is known that the contract requires the existence of two wills, while the bridge bank is assumed to be established by a singular will of the bridge bank, Or is it possible to conclude a contract between the central bank and the defaulting bank, whereby it defines some rights and obligations? This is from one side and on the other side, is the bridge bank possible to take the form of a private company or a public company? This is due to the different laws that govern each of them.

Therefore, we will try to answer the above questions and clarify the legal nature of the bridge bank by dividing this requirement into three sections that we show in the first section, the bridge bank as a private company, and the second section of the bridge bank as a public company. While we allocate the third to consider the bridge bank of a special nature.

First section

Bridge Bank from private companies

Article (4) of the Iraqi Private Companies Law No. (21) for the year (1997) amended in force stipulates that:

First: The company is a contract in which two or more persons are obligated to each of them contribute to an economic project by providing a share of money or work in order to divide the resulting profit or loss.

Second: As an exception to the provisions of Clause (First) of this Article:

1 - The company may consist of one natural person in accordance with the provisions of this law, and such company is hereinafter referred to as (the sole proprietorship).

2- A limited liability company may be established by a single owner in accordance with the provisions of this law.

It is clear from the foregoing texts that the principle is that the company consists of a contract between several parties, and the exception is the possibility of establishing a company from one person, as in the case of a sole proprietorship and a one-person company with limited liability.

If we are either several people, the matter is not without the preparation of a contract between them for the purpose of establishing the company, and this is what Article (13) of the same law referred to, which states that: The contract shall include as a minimum:-...).

But in the event that we are in front of one party, the matter requires preparing a statement for the purpose of completing the incorporation procedures, and this is indicated by Article (14) of the same law, which states that: (The founder of a limited liability company, when the company has no other founders, or The founder of the sole proprietorship shall prepare a statement that takes the place of the company's contract and the provisions that apply to the contract shall apply to it wherever they are mentioned in this law).

Referring to the Banking Law No. (94) of (2004), specifically the texts related to the bridge bank, we find that Article (67/a) stipulates that:

1-The Central Bank of Iraq shall, according to its choice, establish and license a temporary bank based on Article (61/6), which is owned and managed by the Central Bank of Iraq...).

Paragraph (3) of the same article stipulates that (... this board shall implement the contract of incorporation of the interim bank...).

Therefore, it is clear from the foregoing that the bridge bank is not a private company and is not subject to the provisions of the aforementioned Private Companies Law No. (21) of 1997, since the Banking Law, as we have indicated under Article (67/a) above, is established by the Central Bank of Iraq and is managed by it Hence it is considered its owner.

As for mentioning the phrase “the establishment contract of the interim bank”, it does not fit with the nature of its establishment by the unilateral will of the Central Bank, and then this paragraph must be amended, and the phrase “incorporation statement” should be mentioned instead of the articles of incorporation.

Especially after the Registrar of Companies refused to register Hammurabi Bridge Bank as a joint stock company, and the Real Estate Registration Department refused to transfer real estate and the rest of the assets belonging to the troubled Bank of Dar Al Salam to the bridge bank.

We also do not know how to request registration as a joint stock company, especially since the Companies Law requires subscription in the event of establishing a joint stock company, whether private or mixed?.

Second section

The bridge bank is a public company

A public company is defined under Article (1) of the Public Companies Law No. (22) of 1997 as:

(The self-financed economic unit fully owned by the state that enjoys legal personality and financial and administrative independence and operates according to economic foundations).

Article (3) of the same law indicated that the establishment of a public company shall be through a request submitted by the competent ministry to the Council of Ministers, provided that this request is accompanied by a study that includes the technical and economic reasons for its establishment.

If the Council of Ministers approves, the company is considered a contract or a statement, and the contract is only a formality according to the opinion of some, because in the end, the company is affiliated with one person, which is the state.

As for its administrative independence. This means that it has a special apparatus that manages it and is not managed by the state or the legal persons that established it because the state wants to benefit from the provisions of the Companies Law in managing these companies. This special organ that handles the management of the public company is the Board of Directors () and it was stated in Article (19) of the Public Companies Law that “The Board of Directors shall draw up and develop the administrative, technical, organizational and technical policies and plans necessary for the conduct of the company’s activity, achieving its objectives, supervising and following up its implementation, and exercising all rights and the powers related to that, and he may authorize the company’s general manager what he deems appropriate. This means that the task of managing the public company is entrusted to the board of directors. Therefore, it comes to mind that there is no general body for the company, because the public company is established by the state, so it is not possible to imagine the existence of partners consisting of the general assembly as a whole. The public company is also managed by a general manager who is appointed by a decision of the Council of Ministers and is considered the supreme head of the company.

Also, the continuation of public companies in their activities and the permanence of their survival as an economic unit depends on purely economic foundations represented in the profit or efficiency they achieve in investing their funds, because shortcomings lead to their liquidation and expiry, and this is what Article (14) of the Public Companies Law stipulates that (If the loss of the public company reaches 50% of its nominal capital, the ministry must prepare an economic assessment for it to be submitted to the Council of Ministers to take the appropriate decision regarding the continuation or liquidation of the company).

Referring to the Iraqi Banking Law, specifically the provisions related to the bridge bank, we find that Article 61, Paragraph (6) provides that: (Regardless of the requirements contained in Article (14) the Central Bank of Iraq may, at its option, organize a license for a bridge bank that is owned and controlled by the Central Bank of Iraq and receives any assets and liabilities of one or more banks for which the trustee has been appointed pursuant to..... ..termination of its operations after a period of two years from the issuance of a license, except for the Central Bank of Iraq, according to its choice, to extend its legal status for three additional periods of one year).

Also, the purpose of establishing the bridge bank, the circumstances of its establishment, the specific period of its life, and the ways of its expiration are not the same as stipulated in the framework of the public companies law, which was previously referred to above.

Thus, the bridge bank, even if it is stipulated in the Iraqi Banking Law in terms of the public authority that undertakes its establishment and management and has the power to legally terminate it, however, it cannot be applied to all the provisions of public companies, especially since it has characteristics or advantages (already referred to in the first requirement) It does not exist in private companies, not even in public companies, especially since it arises under exceptional circumstances.

Third section

The bridge bank is of a special nature

Since the bridge bank is created, financed, controlled, and even managed by the central bank, this bank must be one of the public banks owned by the state, and therefore it is subject to the provisions of the Public Companies Law in everything that is not mentioned in a special provision in the amended Banking Law of the year 2004 .

However, what should be noted in this regard is that the bridge bank, although it is subject to the provisions of the amended Public Companies Law of 1997, there are some of its provisions that came within the framework of the amended Banking Law of 2004, which represented a departure from the provisions of the Public Companies Law.

Therefore, it can be considered that the bridge bank has a special legal nature that distinguishes it from other public and private companies, and this is reflected in the following:

1- Incorporation procedures: the bridge bank differs from the public company from the start with regard to the incorporation procedures for each of them, which were previously referred to.

2-Determining the capital: Article (61/6) of the amended Banking Law of 2004 stipulates that the Central Bank determines the capital of the bridge bank, unlike what is the case in the framework of public companies, whose capital is determined by a decision of the Council of Ministers. The legislator has also exempted him from the provisions contained in Article 14 of the Banking Law related to capital.

3- Formation of the board of directors of the bridge bank: the central bank is the only one to nominate the members of the board, while the members of the board of directors of the public company are named through the competent minister. While in the context of private companies, this is done in accordance with what is drawn up by law in this regard.

4-In terms of expiration: the Iraqi Banking Law indicated that the bridge bank expires after two years of its establishment, unless its legal existence is extended for three consecutive terms, each of one year, while the amended public companies law of 1997 stipulates that in If certain reasons mentioned in Article (14) of the law are fulfilled, the company will be liquidated after obtaining the approval of the Council of Ministers through the concerned ministry. Thus, the period of apology is one of the most prominent justifications for giving the bridge bank a special nature.

The second topic

The procedures for establishing the bridge-bank

Establishment means a set of legal and material works that require creating the legal structure as desired by the legislator and drawing it through the texts, and these are works carried out by a group of people called “founders”.

The law specified a set of requirements for the establishment of companies of all kinds, public and private, which the Iraqi legislator mentioned in Article (13) of the amended Iraqi Companies Law No. 21 of 1997, as well as Article (3), and Article (6) of the Public Companies Law No. (22) for the year 1997, amended, where, in addition to these requirements, The establishment of banks of all kinds, public and private, requires more complex procedures, such as the approval of the sectoral authority represented by the Central Bank of Iraq, as well as with regard to the minimum capital, and other conditions.

And the procedures for establishing the bridge bank stipulated in the Iraqi Banking Law No. (94) for the year 2004 in force, are in themselves an exception, from the procedures for establishing companies, and establishing banks in particular. For the purpose of taking note of the procedures for establishing the bridge bank, we divide this topic into two demands. We discuss in the first requirement the conditions for establishing the bridge bank, and then we discuss in the second requirement the steps of establishing this bank.

The first requirement

The conditions for establishing the bridge-bank.

By researching the contents of the texts of the Iraqi Banking Law No. (94) of 2004 in force, and Public Companies Law No. (22) of 1997 as amended, as well as Companies Law No. (21) of 1997 as amended, we find that there are conditions for establishing a bridge bank that can be implicitly extracted from the texts of these laws, where we divide this requirement into three sections and as follows:

First section

Having a troubled bank under the tutelage

The bridge bank is not established unless there is a troubled bank placed under tutelage by the central bank as a result of the bank's financial and administrative failures. In other words, the process of establishing the bridge bank shall be preceded by the appointment of a trustee of the bank, and this is clear from the text of Article (67A) of the applicable Banking Law (The Central Bank shall, according to its choice, establish and

license a temporary bank based on Article (61) which is owned and managed by the Central Bank of Iraq to receive any assets and liabilities from one or more banks for which a trustee has been appointed based on Chapter (11) or a judicial receiver under Chapter (14) of the law)Article (61/6) of the same law. Thus, the bridge bank is not established unless the bank is under the tutelage.

Second section

Bank registration

It can be seen from the texts of the amended Public Companies Law No. (22) of 1997 that registration is a prerequisite for the establishment of a public company, as Article (5) of the General Companies Law in force (..the ministry submits a contract or a special statement for the establishment of the company and the approval of the Council of Ministers to the registrar company registration...),Likewise, Article (6) of the same law, which obligated the Registrar of Companies to register the company and issue its certificate of incorporation. The public company also acquires legal personality from the date of issuance of its certificate of incorporation.

The same applies to the establishment of private and mixed joint stock companies subject to the Commercial Companies Law No. (21) of 1997, which requires the company to be registered with the Registrar of Companies, as well as its registration in the Commercial Register.As well as what was stated in the text of Article (5/3) of the effective banking law, obligating companies that have not yet been established to submit a final application to obtain a license to practice banking business after their establishment and registration in the Commercial Register. Companies, as there is no exception for this bank with regard to registration.The exceptions to the bridge bank stipulated in Article (61/6) and (67A) of the effective banking law were related to the capital and its sufficiency mentioned by the legislator in Articles (14) and (16) of the law.

Third section

Bank financing

The law requires the establishment of the bridge bank that there be financing through the provision of the bridge bank with capital by the state, and this is what is stipulated in (67A) of the Banking Law in force (the Central Bank of Iraq establishes and licenses a temporary bank based on Article (67) and provides it with capital by The state...), but this does not mean that the state bears costs, by providing the bank with the capital, but that the bank later bears it to recover its strength, and that the amounts that have been allocated by the state are considered a debt owed by the bank and this is what was confirmed by Article (92) of the effective banking law

The second requirement

The steps for establishing the bridge-bank

Among the procedures that are considered among the operations of maintaining the stability and reputation of the banking system, the legislator authorized in the Banking Law for the Central Bank, according to its choice, to establish and license a bridge bank owned and managed by the Central Bank. The incorporation procedures include a set of steps that can be summed up in three sections, as follows:

First section

License version

The legislator specified in the Banking Law, specifically in Part Two of it, the procedures for obtaining a license to establish a bank in Iraq, where Article (14) of it stipulates, “The establishment of a bank in Iraq is required, including secondary sections that are mostly or completely owned by a foreign bank or a banking company.” Holding a prior banking license issuance from the Ethnic Central Bank...),Therefore, the licensing procedures for the bridge bank are subject to the same procedures as licensing other banks, based on the provisions of Paragraph (4) of Article (67A) of the Banking Law in force, which categorically stipulates that the bridge bank is subject to all provisions of the law for banks except for Article (14) and (16)) related to the minimum capital, and the requirements of articles (30, 31, 33) that pertain to credit concentrations and credit to related persons and high-ranking bank employees, and investment restrictions

Since from our point of view, the legislator had to explicitly exclude the bridge bank from the licensing procedures, especially with regard to the license period, as the license period for the bridge bank is limited to two years from its issuance, unless the central bank, according to its choice, extends the period for three additional periods within a year, unlike other banks whose license period is indefinite, and can only be canceled according to justifications stipulated in Article (13) of the applicable Banking Law

Since the bank is owned by the Central Bank of Iraq, it is competent to regulate its licensing according to the text of Article (61/6) of the Banking Law in force. Contrary to what was stated in Article (3) of the amended Public Companies Law No. (22) of 1997, which requires the approval of the Council of Ministers to establish a public company at the request of the concerned ministry

Second section

Appointment of a board of directors

Paragraph (3) of Article (67A) of the applicable Banking Law stipulates the appointment of a board of directors for the bridge bank by the Central Bank of Iraq, as the legislator did not specify the number of members who comprise the board of directors, nor did he address how they were appointed and the term of their membership, as stipulated The legislator in the law requires that they be fit and suitable persons, that is, they are qualified and have experience in banking

Therefore, the formation of a board of directors for the bridge bank differs from the formation of the board of directors of the public company, in terms of determining the number of board members and the method of their selection

Also, the legislator of the Banking Law in (67A/4/C) granted the authority to the Central Bank of Iraq to appoint or dismiss any high-ranking banking department or employee working in the bridge bank.

Third section

Incorporation statement

The legislator in the Banking Law requires that the bridge bank have a statement of incorporation. As for the phrase (contract of incorporation of the bridge bank), which was mentioned in Article (67a/3), it is contrary to legal logic, since the establishment of the bridge bank is subject to the unilateral will of the Central Bank of Iraq

As the contract requires the presence of two or more legal persons, as the reason for using the memorandum of association is due to the term "Memorandum of Association" in the English version, and it is more correct to use the bank's incorporation statement and not the bank's founding contract.

While the Iraqi legislator was successful in Article (4) of the Public Companies Law No. (22) of 1997, as amended, when obligating the concerned ministry to prepare a contract or statement for the establishment of the public company. This statement or contract is submitted to the Registrar of Companies for registration and issuance of a certificate of incorporation .

The law obligated the board of directors of the bridge bank to implement the statement of incorporation, after it was approved by the Central Bank of Iraq.

The Third topic

Mechanisms for saving the troubled bank

After completing the establishment of the bridge bank in order to save the troubled bank, practical steps must be taken through which the bad situation can be rectified and what can be saved. The first of these steps is represented in either transferring assets and liabilities from the troubled bank to the bridge bank in full, or appointing a judicial guard if necessary. As for the second of these steps, it is the search for the extent of the possibility of converting the bank to another company and capitalizing its debts or continuing its banking activity without switching to another company. Accordingly, we will divide this topic into two demands. In the first requirement, we will show the transfer of assets and liabilities from the troubled bank to the bridge bank. While we allocate the second requirement to convert the bank to another company or the continuation of its activity.

The first requirement

Transfer of assets and liabilities from the troubled bank to the bridge bank

The original is the transfer of assets and liabilities from the troubled bank to the bridge bank in full, but the law permitted to preserve some of them, according to the nature of the case, either under the hands of the guardian or a judicial guard appointed for this purpose. Accordingly, this requirement will be divided into two sections. In the first section, we show the complete transfer of assets and liabilities. While we allocate the second section to keep it under the hands of the guardian or the judicial guard.

First section

Transfer of assets and liabilities in full

The financial liability of banks consists of assets and liabilities, and it is well known that these banks own assets that are different in terms of their nature and impact. In terms of nature, there are financial assets represented by stocks, bonds and bank deposits, and in return there are physical assets such as real estate and other property. As for the liabilities, they are the financial and non-financial obligations that the bank must fulfill, such as bank deposits and others

Therefore, the competent authorities, such as the Central Bank of Iraq and the Deposit Keeping Corporation in the United States of America, transfer those assets and liabilities after studying them well and choosing what is suitable for transfer to the bridge bank if it is curable, and this is what the Iraqi legislator

referred to in the Banking Law No. 94 of 2004 and the US Depository Materials Depository Act Sec. 1821(n)(1)(B) and Sec. 1921 (n)(3)(A)(i,ii) . Referring to these texts, they can be summarized as follows

1- The Central Bank of Iraq and the Deposit Custody Corporation in the United States of America, after the establishment of the bridge bank, shall carefully study the reality of the troubled bank, relying on the trustee's report.

2- After that, all or some of those assets and liabilities are transferred to the bridge bank management in order to preserve the reputation of the troubled bank, as well as to preserve the depositors' money and to fulfill the outstanding debts.

3- The Central Bank may, in accordance with Article (67-3), order the trustee to transfer part or all of the bank's assets and liabilities to an intermediary bank.

4- The transfer of transactions from the assets and liabilities of the troubled bank to the bridge bank must be published in the Official Gazette and in the local newspapers in order to notify the relevant parties that their accounts and transactions have been transferred to the bridge bank, as well as in order to give an opportunity to claim depositors for their deposits and know their fate.

It is clear from the foregoing that the process of transferring assets and liabilities from the troubled bank to the bridge bank has been regulated by the relevant laws, as shown above, to guarantee the rights of depositors and reassure individuals, however, that these assets and liabilities may not be transferred completely, but rather are taken care of by the guardian or custodian This is what will be the subject of our discussion in the next section of this requirement.

Second Section

Placing assets and liabilities under the custody of a trustee or receiver

We stated above that the principle is the transfer of material and immaterial assets and liabilities from the troubled bank to the bridge bank in order to preserve them and ensure the rights of depositors and their development as much as possible. However, the law has permitted the exclusion of some of the bank's obligations towards its creditors from this transfer and entrusted that task with the trustee, provided that the interest of the creditors is taken into account, as indicated in Article (67-a-1) of the Iraqi Banking Law No. 94 of 2004.

The aforementioned law also permitted that those assets and liabilities be placed under the hands of a judicial receiver under Chapter Fourteen of the said law.

It is clear from the foregoing that the Central Bank of Iraq has a choice between keeping the remaining assets and liabilities with the trustee or asking the court to appoint a judicial guard in accordance with Article 80 of the Iraqi Banking Law No. 94 of 2004. If the judicial receiver undertakes the supervision and follow-up of the assets and liabilities that have not been transferred from the troubled bank to the bridge bank, in accordance with the directives issued by the Central Bank of Iraq in this regard.

The approach in jurisprudence and the American judiciary is not much different from that, as jurisprudence refers to closing the troubled bank and transferring its assets and liabilities that are not transferred to the bridge bank to a judicial guard under the supervision and follow-up by the Deposit Custody Corporation. The main reason behind keeping these assets and not transferring them is that they suffer from problems and the opportunity to improve and develop them is less than others, as in the case of non-performing loans and assets subject to lawsuits and other assets that are difficult to develop

We conclude from the foregoing that the assets and liabilities of the troubled bank are either transferred completely to the bridge bank under the supervision of the Central Bank of Iraq and the American Banking Deposit Corporation based on the trustee's report after studying and indicating the extent to which they can be reformed, developed and benefited from by paying creditors' debts, or some Including under the supervision of the guardian or the receiver.

The second requirement

The transformation of the troubled bank or the continuation of its activities

The troubled bank is going through a dangerous stage in its life. It is either transforming and capitalizing its debts, or continuing its activity with the possibility of addressing the problems it faces, so we will try to divide this requirement into two sections. The first section is the transformation of the bank and the capitalization of its debts, while we allocate the second section to the continuation of the bank's activities, as shown below:

First section

Transformation of the bank and capitalization of its debts

The competent authorities, such as the Central Bank of Iraq and the American Deposit Keeping Corporation, may see that rehabilitating a faltering bank requires large sums of money to be able to restart it in a way that can manage the bridge bank to advance the reality of the faltering bank and find the necessary solutions to its crises,

but is available to it of cash liquidity and positive assets It does not fulfil the purpose of converting the bank and capitalizing its debts.

Therefore, we find that the Central Bank of Iraq, in its first experience regarding the bridge bank, announced in the founding book that Hammurabi Bank would complete all procedures related to communicating with creditors in order to obtain their final approval to capitalize their debts. As for the creditors who do not wish to capitalize their debts, they remain with the Dar Al-Salaam Investment Bank. It is clear from this that the Central Bank of Iraq was destined to capitalize debts from the beginning, and capitalization is known as (A legal act according to which the bank contract is amended by increasing its capital during the life of the bank, in accordance with the methods and procedures specified by the system)

It is clear from the foregoing that transferring part of the bank's debts to its capital (capitalizing it) so that the creditors become shareholders in the management of the bank, i.e. converting debts to its shares in the capital.

Debt capitalization is one of the most important ways to increase capital in companies, and it is a step that the board of directors must take, as it entails increasing cash liquidity on the one hand and raising debts on the other hand, after it becomes shares for creditors

As for the legal basis for increasing the capital (debt capitalization), we find that the Iraqi legislator in the Public Companies Law No. 22 of 1997 has permitted increasing or decreasing the capital of the public company, but he did not refer to the ways to increase the capital, including converting debts into shares. The Iraqi Banking Law authorized the Central Bank to increase the capital of the bridge bank under Article (67-4-b). However, he did not explain to us the mechanisms of the increase and did not draw the way for us in this regard, and this indicates that the legislator did not clearly allow the capitalization of debts for the troubled bank and its conversion into shares. We believe that debt capitalization as a method of increasing the capital of the troubled bank is still missing its legal basis, given that the Private Companies Law No. 21 of 1997 amended by Coalition Authority Order No. 64 of 2004 did not include a mechanism for converting debts into shares

Second section

Continuing the activity of the troubled bank

We stated above that the first option that can be followed regarding the troubled bank is the capitalization of debts, i.e. converting debts into shares. However, that path has great risks and complicated procedures with a weak legal basis for this according to the legislation in force. As for the other option, which seems to be the most appropriate and harmonious to address the situation of the troubled bank by supporting the bridge bank during the rehabilitation period until the course is corrected.

Where the Iraqi legislator indicated in the Banking Law No. 94 of 2004 the necessity of obligating the trustee during his work in maximizing the proceeds of sale or disposing of the assets of the troubled bank or reducing any loss to it. And to treat the creditor on an equal footing and to enhance the returns of the troubled bank and reduce its losses, all through the assets and liabilities transferred to it, in accordance with Articles (67-3), (61-7) and (61-6)

The Iraqi Banking Law in Article (67 - A - 6) also obligated the bridge bank management not to carry out any act or transaction regarding the assets and liabilities of the troubled bank or any change in its system and regulations except after the approval of the Central Bank of Iraq.

Therefore, operating the bridge bank in this way without resorting to debt capitalization is the option also in force in the United States of America through the US Federal Depository Corporation, As most of the experiences that happened to them did not resort to capitalizing the debts of the troubled bank, nor did they enter into changing the nature of the bridge bank. In order for the bridge bank to succeed and to continue its operation, it must accept deposits, offer new loans, mix them with existing accounts, and shorten some contractual obligations that the troubled bank had previously registered itself with. And all of this without the need to increase the capital and be satisfied with what it has

Finally, the Banking Law has set a specific period during which the bridge bank, which was found in exceptional circumstances, must end in order to save a troubled bank from collapsing. Whereas Article (61-6) of the aforementioned law indicated that the life of the bridge bank ends within a period of two years from the date of issuing its license, except in the case that the central bank, according to its choice, extends its legal status (for three periods) for an additional one year.

It is also possible to terminate the work in the bridge bank by legal action away from the expiry of the aforementioned period, through one of the following cases

- 1- The success of the rehabilitation plan, in terms of financial and administrative terms, and making the necessary corrections and treatments, which would enable the troubled bank to take the initiative and resume its banking activity again.
- 2- Obtaining a new buyer in order to buy the troubled bank after its assets and litigation with the bridge bank continued, all in order to get rid of the risk of bankruptcy and liquidation of troubled banks and to reassure depositors.

- 3- Merging the troubled bank with another bank and consolidating it.
- 4- 4- Forced liquidation of the defaulting bank, in accordance with Article (69) of the Iraqi Banking Law, after exhausting the legal avenues for filing a bankruptcy lawsuit. That is, the bankruptcy lawsuit must be filed first. If it does not succeed for any of the reasons indicated in Article 57 of the Iraqi Banking Law, then it is possible to go directly to the forced liquidation procedures in accordance with Articles (69) and (77) of the said law.

Conclusion:

After we have finished this research, we must refer to some of the results and recommendations that we have reached, which are as follows:

- 1- Iraqi legislation, prior to the issuance of Banking Law No. 94 of 2004, did not mention the bridge banking system and banking guardianship over troubled banks. Likewise, the banking laws in most Arab countries did not provide for the bridge banking system or the guardianship of troubled banks.
- 2- It is clear from this study that the bridge bank is a public bank whose ownership is desired by the state represented by the Central Bank of Iraq. And that the period of work of the bridge bank is a temporary period, and the Iraqi legislator has specified two years, renewable for one year and in three stages. That is why it was called the Interim Bank, meaning that it was established in order to save the troubled bank and then end its work.
- 3- It is clear from the text of Article (61/6) of the Iraqi Banking Law No. 94 of 2004 that the Central Bank has the authority to oblige the trustee to transfer all or part of the assets by the trustee to the bridge bank management.
- 4- The Iraqi Banking Law No. 94 of 2004 in Article (67 A/3) stipulates the formation of a board of directors for the bridge bank, and that the Central Bank is the authority authorized to form this board.

Recommendations:

- 1- We recommend that the Iraqi legislator grant the Central Bank the power to forcibly merge troubled banks and not be satisfied with taking measures of forced liquidation or bankruptcy.
- 2- We suggest to the Iraqi legislator to put a clear and specific definition of the bridge bank that does not tolerate ambiguity or ambiguity.
- 3- We suggest to the Iraqi legislator to give the authority to extend the work of the bridge bank to the board of directors (the board of directors of the bridge bank) because the board of directors is informed in detail and practically of all the details of the work of this bank and according to what this board deems appropriate.

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